

Tooth-Supported Overdentures : A Practical and Cost-Effective Alternative to Implant-Supported Dentures – A Case Report

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Abstract

This case reports presents the use of tooth-supported overdenture as a practical and cost-effective alternative to implant-supported dentures. The advantages of using existing healthy teeth as abutments to enhance prosthesis retention, stability and proprioception along with preservation of bone structure are accentuated. The first case is of a 48-year-old patient with missing mandibular teeth, due to caries and periodontal disease, aiming for a more retentive prosthesis. The tooth supported overdenture with metal coping improved masticatory efficiency and retention as compared to previous removable partial dentures. The second case presents the treatment of a 60-year-old patient with a Ceka-attachmentretained overdenture.

Keywords : Tooth supported overdenture, proprioception, retention, Ceka attachment.

Introduction

Preventive prosthodontics aims to alleviate future complications in dental structures, such as teeth and bone. Overdentures are significant in providing alternatives that delay resorption in the alveolar bone, enhance proprioception, and improve the area of support for prostheses. The concept of overdentures is more than a century old. Henking mentioned that Ledger and Atkinson were early exponents of leaving ‘stumps’ of teeth under dentures for support¹. Later, Reitz et al² cited that J.B. Beers patented a telescopic crown in 1873, while Schweitzer et al³ reported that by 1887, Peeso had described removable telescopic bridgework. Augsburg referred to Hall and Gilmore, who described bar-splinted abutment teeth for supporting dentures thus initiating the idea of attachment-supported overdentures⁴. Dolder⁵ further popularized the bar and clip-retained overdenture in the 1950s. Miller⁶ revived interest in the use of the telescopic overdenture, proposing primary and secondary gold copings over the abutments for better retention. Yalisove⁷ developed the crown and sleeve coping retainers for overdentures.

The development of such ideas added to the evolution of the design. Some physiological benefits of natural teeth or roots retained under the prosthesis are preservation of the alveolar bone, improved masticatory efficiency, and better proprioception. Atwood¹⁴ observed that RRR

after teeth loss is a chronic and progressive process, whereas Loisselle et al.¹⁵ demonstrated no change in the height of the anterior alveolar ridge in patients for whom complete lower overdentures were worn over two years. This case reports presents overdentures as a feasible alternative for patients with retainable teeth.

Case Report¹

A 48-year-old patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics in Mansarovar dental college, Bhopal for getting his missing teeth replaced due to difficulties in mastication. The patient had fixed partial denture in maxillary arch with tooth number 11, 12, 13, 14, 21, 22, 23, 24. Mandibular arch was partially edentulous with Kennedy class I modification 1. Tooth number 33, 34 and 43 were present in mandibular arch. The patient gave a history of teeth loss over a period of 15 years due to multiple caries and periodontal problems. He had worn removable partial dentures during this period. No mobility and periodontal pathology were noticed in the clinical and radiographical examination.

Treatment Plan and Procedure

A tentative jaw relation of the diagnostic casts was done to assess the inter-arch space; It was found to be sufficient for an

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overdenture with short copings but less for a bar supported overdenture. After intentional root canal treatment of 33,34 and 44, they were prepared with tapered round end diamond point bur & a chamfer finish line was placed subgingivally. An addition silicon rubber base(GC FLEXCEED) impression was made. Metal copings were then fabricated and cemented

Fig 1. Intraoral Photograph

Fig 2. Final Impression Record

Fig 3 Orientation Jaw Relation

Fig 4. Overdenture Prosthesis

on the abutment tooth with help of luting GIC. Special tray was fabricated using self-cure acrylic resin. Border moulding was done with low fusing compound and final impression was made with medium body elastomer. Master casts were prepared by pouring the impressions with Type IV dental stone. Copings on the master cast were covered with wax and record base was fabricated after applying separating media. Placement of wax over abutments was done to prevent the fracture of the cast during removal of the temporary record base. Occlusal rims were fabricated and maxillomandibular relations were recorded and transferred onto the semi-adjustable articulator with the help of face-bow. Teeth setting was done, evaluated in the patient's mouth for phonetics,

vertical and centric relation along with aesthetics. Patient's approval was taken, and the denture was acrylicized using heat-cure acrylic resin. Final denture was then finished, polished & inserted in patient's mouth and corrections are done.

Case Report²

A male patient aged 60-year-old, having lost his teeth because of caries over a span of 10 years wanted a prosthesis with more stability than the previous removable prostheses. Teeth 33, 34, 37, 38 and 43, 48 were present. Radiographic examination revealed enough bone support and teeth had long and slender roots. The patient was informed about various treatment modalities including flexible denture, cast partial denture, implant supported over denture and tooth supported attachment retained prosthesis. The patient was treated with tooth supported attachment retained over denture prosthesis.

Treatment Plan and Procedure

The treatment was completed in two phases i.e. endodontic phase and prosthetic phase respectively. Diagnostic impressions were made for both arches using irreversible hydrocolloid (Algitex Heraeus Kulzer, South bend IN), the impressions were poured with type IV gypsum. Intentional root canal treatment of tooth number 33 and 43 were performed in order to aid as an abutment for overdenture. After that, the teeth were reduced to the level of gingiva and post space was created in relation to 33 and 43 according to the manufacturer's guidelines (Ceka Perci-line, Belgium). After the preparation of post spaces, the radicular ball attachments (Ceka Perci-line Belgium) were cemented using glass ionomer luting cement (GC gold label Luting cement). Final Impressions were made and orientation jaw relation was recorded using a facebow and centric record transferred onto the semi-adjustable articulator, followed by teeth arrangement. The try-in was done and final denture was acrylicized, finished and polished.

The female counterparts were placed to the mandibular denture using the direct technique. Metal sleeves were placed over the ball attachments, and adjustments were made to the mandibular denture to ensure a smooth fit without any interference. Once the denture was properly positioned, the metal sleeves were fixed onto the denture using a self-cure acrylic resin, and nylon O-rings were inserted into the metal sleeves to secure them in place.

The mandibular denture was inserted in patient mouth and adjustments were done. Post insertion instructions were given to the patient and the patient was recalled after 24 hours.

Fig 1 Intraoral Photograph

Fig 2. Orientation Jaw Relation

Fig 7. Overdenture insertion

Fig 3. Try in

Fig 4. Ceka Attachment Placement

Fig 5. Metal Housing For Attachment

Fig. 6 metal sleeves fixing followed by nylon o-ring placement

Discussion

The basic foundation of the overdenture treatment lies in the abutment teeth providing better support and anchorage to the prosthesis, along with maintaining proprioception and preventing resorption. Miller⁶ initially stated that retaining teeth under a prosthesis can contribute to the retardation of the resorption process. But later on, Atwood¹⁴ confirmed that, after the extraction of teeth, residual ridge resorption is inevitable, though retaining roots under overdentures does tend to minimize such bone loss. Also, Loisel et al.¹⁵ found no measurable difference in the height of the alveolar ridge in patients wearing overdentures for a two-year period, a fact that points to the advantage of retaining the teeth.

Mensor⁸ in 1973, classified the different types of overdenture attachments. Pacer et al.¹⁸ detected that patients with overdentures have better load discrimination than complete denture wearers. Manly¹⁶ mentioned that the oral mucosa has less proprioceptive capability as compared to the PDL receptors preserved in overdenture wearers. Similarly, Dodge¹⁷ reported that the periodontal sense from the overdenture prosthesis allows better manipulation of it and gives an increase in the precision of the movements of the jaw. Levin¹⁹ compared natural dentitions, overdentures, and complete dentures based on proprioception: he found that the patients with natural dentition had acute perception, followed by the patients with overdentures, and finally the wearers of complete dentures. Renner et al.²⁰ also discussed how roots retained under overdentures avoid the 'anterior hyperfunction syndrome'.

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